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Table of Contents

1	Document overview	5
1.1	Objectives.....	5
1.2	Scope	6
1.3	Guidelines for Optimizing Data Integration and Interoperability in Cultural Heritage Projects	7
2	User need's	8
3	Accessibility of Nile Valley Religious Texts in Digital Repositories	10
3.1	Data	13
4	Interoperability and Mapping	18
4.1	Standards.....	20
5	Data Integration	24
5.1	Europeana Data Model (EDM)	25
5.2	Description of archaeological data, the case of AO-Cat	28
5.3	Description of inscription, the case of EAGLE	32
5.4	Schema.org.....	35
5.5	Integrating text and supports: CIDOC-CRMtex.....	37
6	Magic-Therapeutic Bowls: A Case Study of Art, Text, and New Technologies	40
	Conclusions	43
	References.....	43

List of Tables

Table 1 Overview of the data standards and vocabularies in the analyzed digital archives	21
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List of Figures

Figure 1 Datatype published by digital archives	16
Figure 2 Process for data aggregation	19
Figure 3 The three core classes of EDM. Europeana data-Model guidelines v.2.4	26
Figure 4 Schema for the description of archaeological data in the AO-Cat ontology	29
Figure 5 Entities and relationships in archaeological domain	31
Figure 6 Descriptive elements of epigraphic material	32
Figure 7 High-level model	33
Figure 8 Eagle aggregator coceptual model	35
Figure 9 CRMTex model	39

1 Document overview

1.1 Objectives

The main goal of WP10 ReTINA is to enhance the RESILIENCE infrastructure by implementing a shared data model and developing a prototype software for user interaction, based on religious content datasets from ancient world sites along and beyond the Nile Valley. This objective will be pursued by creating guidelines derived from diverse datasets. ReTINA addresses a gap in the digital description and accessibility of ancient religious texts from archaeological contexts, fostering a more structured and interoperable approach to their study and dissemination. The specificity of the field of religious studies, where the cultural significance of texts and objects must often be linked to specific theological factors, allows for the consideration of descriptors that go beyond the merely linguistic and religious level and can lay the groundwork for the creation of further digitization work. In the field of religious studies, the cultural significance of texts and objects is often deeply intertwined with specific rituals, symbolic and also magical actors. This complexity requires a descriptive approach that extends beyond purely linguistic or descriptive categorizations, incorporating elements such as liturgical functions, magical practices and historical transmission contexts. By integrating these broader descriptors, it becomes possible to develop a more comprehensive framework for analyzing religious artifacts and texts.

The Nile Valley case study represents a microcosm (serves as a representative model) that can be extended to other equally (or more) fragmented contexts. Hence, ReTINA seeks to expand knowledge and deepen the understanding of religious texts and objects beyond the Nile Valley, fostering a broader and more interconnected perspective on their significance and interpretation.

This enriched approach not only enhances the depth and accuracy of digital representations but also provides a solid foundation for future digitization efforts. By establishing structured methodologies that account for theological and cultural dimensions, researchers can create more interoperable datasets, facilitating cross-disciplinary studies and ensuring that digital resources more accurately reflect the multifaceted nature of religious heritage.

ReTINA will, therefore, strengthen RESILIENCE by providing research enhancement services, particularly those dedicated to digitization tools, data integration, and information retrieval.

Reviewing the state of the art will identify what data models are prevalent in the religious studies community and outline a pattern that can support principles and, more broadly, the goals of Open Science.

1.2 Scope

This deliverable is a report on the work done under WP10. It includes the tasks carried out over the past six months as a result of the findings described in D10.1 and is based on the first version of the recommended data management practices and guidelines for RESILIENCE¹. The deliverable provides guidelines for users such as data providers and researchers for producing standardized data and suggests the possible trajectories for the integration of different datasets regardless of their origin or format. The focus is on the digital archiving of datasets characterized by religious texts written on various supports. The integration of these diverse datasets is a relatively new approach, encompassing not only manuscripts but also archaeological artifacts from various historical periods. These periods are marked by a fluid and evolving understanding of religion, where religious concepts are often intertwined with and inseparable from other aspects of the communities that shaped them, such as social, political, and economic factors.

Defining an object or text as religious requires careful consideration of multiple factors, especially in the case of archaeological artifacts and, more generally, of the material culture (Merrifield 1987; Insoll 2004; Riley Augé 2022). The function of such an object is often deeply influenced by its archaeological context, which plays a critical role in shaping how both the object and any text associated with it are interpreted. The context not only determines the practical or symbolic role the object may have had in its original setting but also influences our understanding of its significance within the broader cultural, social, and religious practices of the community that produced it. According to post-processual archaeology, meaning is not inherent in an artifact but emerges through its relationships with space, ritual practices, and human experience. This approach challenges the idea of fixed, universal meanings. Instead, it emphasizes that beliefs and symbolic associations are deeply embedded in specific cultural contexts. Rather than imposing modern assumptions, archaeologists must reconstruct meaning by examining not just the object itself, but also its surroundings, its use, and its role in social interactions. Ultimately, understanding whether an artifact had a religious or magical function requires more than a material analysis—it demands an exploration of its spatial, cultural, and symbolic context. Consequently, the classification of these artifacts as 'religious' is often not straightforward and demands a nuanced reading of the material evidence alongside the textual content. From this perspective it is important to reflect on the technical procedures and on the appropriate data model that describe and enhance the datasets, as well as on their integration for a correct reuse of data. The present document is structured according to the activities carried out by the work package and aims to explore the integration and interoperability of archaeological and epigraphic data within digital environments. It begins by outlining the objectives and scope of the project, clarifying its purpose and the expected

¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/15025213>

outcomes. A key focus is on understanding user needs, ensuring that the methodologies and data structures align with practical requirements.

1.3 Guidelines for Optimizing Data Integration and Interoperability in Cultural Heritage Projects

In order to create an environment that in first place optimizes common guidelines for the digitization and digital archiving of such a diverse array of sources, accounting for the challenges posed by the different languages and writing support types, two actions are important:

- ✓ to provide evidence of user's needs;
- ✓ to select the most commonly used data models that allow for the integration of such heterogeneous datasets.

Thus, the primary objective is to analyze existing data models and similar initiatives implemented within the cultural heritage sector. The survey conducted during the initial months of the project² identified a wide range of datasets with diverse characteristics, each described using different standards for the formal representation of knowledge. Many of these datasets are aggregated within infrastructures designed to integrate and harmonize data, creating a unified environment where users can efficiently search for information. These infrastructures provide access to key metadata about each dataset and facilitate consultation through dedicated landing pages, which link to the content providers' websites—such as museums, universities, and other institutions. This approach not only streamlines access to the data but also enhances interoperability across diverse domains, making it easier to cross-reference and analyze information from different sources.

Based on the survey results, this deliverable presents a variety of strategies and procedures utilized by different projects. Some of these projects are highly interdisciplinary or focused on specific sectors and were developed without standardized guidelines. The current objective is to provide guidelines along with technical and conceptual tools for organizing resources, enhancing the integration and interoperability of datasets, all in accordance with the principles of Open Science and FAIR data.

Open Science is based on the idea that “scientific research, data and dissemination are accessible to all levels of inquiring society” and is about increased transparency, re-use, participation, cooperation, accountability and reproducibility for research. Research data and processes are freely available, under terms that enable reuse, redistribution and reproduction of the research and its underlying data and methods.

In 2014, in order to define the best practice recommendation for research data, a core set of FAIR principles were drafted. They ensure that data or any digital object are Findable: using

² See Deliverable D10.1 <https://zenodo.org/records/15025213>

machine-readable persistent identifiers (PIDs) and metadata that allows the automatic and reliable discovery of datasets and services; **Accessible**: using a standardized and open communications protocol; **Interoperable**: using formats that are open and allow the combination and use of data with other data and tools. The data should be able to be combined with and used with other data or tools; and **Re-usable**: well-describing metadata and data so that they can be replicated and/or combined in different settings.

The methodology section details the approach taken to collect, analyze, and organize data, emphasizing the importance of standardization and consistency. Interoperability is a central theme, with an in-depth discussion on data mapping and the adoption of key standards to facilitate seamless exchange between different systems.

A significant portion of the document is therefore dedicated to data integration strategies, highlighting the use of the Europeana Data Model (EDM) and various case studies, such as AO-Cat for archaeological data and EAGLE for inscriptions. The document also examines how the CIDOC-CRMtex model is applied within the ReTina project to enhance textual documentation, and how Schema.org improves data discoverability on digital platforms.

Finally, the study of a set of magic-therapeutic bowls serves as a case study demonstrating the intersection of art, text, and new technologies. This example illustrates how digital tools can be used to analyze and preserve cultural heritage, showcasing the broader implications of the project.

2 User need's

The religious studies community includes a plurality of researchers spanning different domains that cross diachronically the ancient and modern worlds and synchronically different geographical areas, languages and cultures. In addition, the basis of studies is not always limited to texts (manuscripts or epigraphs) written in different types of media and that have come down to the present day. Often the sacred refers to otherworldly or divine phenomena enhanced by intangible experiences (e.g., dance, song, prayer) or ritual, cultic and/or magical objects found in areas consecrated to the deity (temples, shrines, springs or sacred places, oracles). Certain typology of household finds may take on a special curative, therapeutic or otherworldly function when they are used by priests in particular ritual contexts. Sacred and profane, therefore, are intertwined to the point that it is almost impossible, especially for the ancient world, to distinguish the use value of objects when decontextualized; only the area of discovery can allow the correct identification of the material find and its belonging to the earthly or divine sphere. While a sacred text or religious formula found on an epigraph appears to be the explicit manifestation of a relationship with the divine world, the sacred object is often difficult to recognize and classify in the absence of distinctive features or without an understanding of its original

context. This difficulty in identifying the characterizing elements of a material object used in a sacred setting is reflected in an uncertainty in the categorization of the artifacts, frequently recorded as mere forms of common or commercial use thus losing their sometimes-temporary charge of sacredness. Given these challenges, it is common to refer exclusively to a morpho typological framework. While this approach can be useful in certain cases, it often oversimplifies the complexity of sacred objects by concentrating primarily on their physical form or type, rather than their ritualistic or symbolic importance within a specific cultural or religious context. As a result, essential aspects related to the sacredness of these objects may be overlooked, leading to an incomplete understanding of their role and significance in the sacred space. This limitation highlights the need for more refined categorization systems that can address both the material qualities of these objects and their evolving cultural and spiritual meaning over time.

The survey performed in D10.1 confirmed this critical issue as the large online digital archives related to the civilizations that developed in the Nile Valley and beyond do not seem to assign this particular type of objects a specific category, thus making it difficult to find them. Metadata, which ideally provides key information about the artifact—such as its origin, provenance, historical context, and condition—is essential for ensuring the accuracy and depth of any analysis. Without this crucial layer of information, researchers are left with incomplete data, which can lead to misinterpretations or the inability to draw meaningful conclusions. Furthermore, the lack of reference contexts exacerbates this issue. When artifacts are presented without a clear historical, cultural, or archaeological framework, they lose their broader significance. Researchers are deprived of the necessary background that would allow them to place these objects within the appropriate historical or cultural narrative. This lack of context not only hinders the scholarly understanding of individual artifacts but also impedes the potential for cross-disciplinary connections, making it more difficult to link the artifact to other related works or research fields.

While the traditional needs of digital data users appear to be focused on the following:

- Lack of metadata or quality metadata;
- Limitations or barriers to accessing and reusing the digital source;
- Difficulty in performing cross-searching in the absence of integration policies;

the sphere of religious studies adds additional problematic issues that we can summarize as:

- Obstacles to find specific classes of objects related to the sacred;
- Need for quality metadata for textual content (epigraph/manuscript) and media (pottery, metal objects, statues, etc.);
- Absence of reference contexts;
- Multilingualism and multiculturalism often resulting in semantic polysemy.

In order to overcome the listed critical issues, it is necessary to develop best practices that invest both the design and construction of a portal, ora aggregator, and the organization and presentation of the data.

On the interface side, it is necessary to provide the user with a set of functions to:

- Search, in a guided and flexible manner, for any type of data by creating lists of tabs with thumbnails of images and 3D models attached;
- Create and customize lists of data that can be stored and updated later by the user;
- Share lists with other scholars;
- Correct and filter images;
- Interactively navigate 3D models;
- Annotate images and/or 3D models;
- Download metadata of selected objects.

The portal is to be configured as a metadata aggregator on the model of Europeana, having services in a multilingual mode. The metadata will have to include, according to FAIR data principles:

- a digital persistent identifier;
- a standard data-model accessible by a human user and a machine;
- a license specifying their reuse.

Finally, if possible, metadata should be enriched through the use of standard thesauri.

3 Accessibility of Nile Valley Religious Texts in Digital Repositories

This work is based on the survey described in D10.1. The primary focus of the survey was to document, within the ReTINA project, the archives - already published online - that contain records related to religious texts from the expansive region of the Nile Valley and beyond.

The survey collected information about current practices used to publish and access to artistic, archaeological, epigraphical and philological data. The information was gathered by simply accessing the website pages as a regular user, without contacting the site administrators. That is why our purpose was not only to observe data from the organizational perspective but also to understand the level of data integration, interoperability and how it was treated the religious topic.

According to those purposes, the survey mainly focused on digital archives and repositories of various heritage institutions including 14 museums where physical objects are preserved, 6 universities, 5 institutes. Some institutions deposit data in repositories or aggregate

datasets in specific infrastructures. About projects, 15 involve multiple institutions, and they consist of databases, service platforms, and digital archives.

The analysis of the survey reveals that textual resources from the Nile Valley are preserved in numerous museums and institutions, primarily originating from archaeological investigations. However, it is important to note that not all institutions that collect materials from the Nile Valley are represented in this survey. The survey aimed to understand how the relevant materials, which are often part of larger museum collections, have been managed and digitized. Consequently, collections that do not have their materials available online were not included in this survey. Nonetheless, it is essential to acknowledge the existence of many non-digitized and offline collections that could be integrated into the infrastructure in the future. In this context, establishing guidelines may prove beneficial for facilitating the integration of these datasets down the line.

In this regard, the establishment of standardized guidelines for digitization and data integration would be highly beneficial. Such guidelines would not only facilitate the inclusion of currently unavailable datasets but also ensure consistency in data structuring and accessibility, thereby enhancing interoperability across institutions and research platforms.

The survey indicates that out of the 40 digital archives listed in D10.1, which collect and publish datasets, some employ a metadata aggregation approach. *MuseiD-Italia*, site that however is no longer accessible since the beginning of 2024, published for example some resources from the Egyptian Collection of the Museo Archeologico Nazionale di Napoli (MANN), that would otherwise not be accessible online because the museum opted to display only a narrow range of objects from its large and varied collections. *Trismegistos* platform³ aggregates metadata and provides services, for example, allowing a search starting from the deity's name. The metadata aggregation approach consists of a central organization that takes the role of facilitating the discovery and use of the resources by collecting their associated metadata (Freire et al. 2018). This approach is used in the domain of the cultural heritage.

The dispersion of these materials across institutions worldwide, combined with the way they are published, makes it difficult to search for and identify relevant datasets. Often, these materials are digitized and made available as small, independent collections within larger digital archives, where they are grouped alongside various other types of resources. This is particularly evident in museums, where textual or archaeological datasets are frequently integrated into broader collections without distinct categorization.

³ <https://www.trismegistos.org/>

As Niccolucci (2020, 41) pointed out, this situation is further complicated by the limitations of major search engines like Google. While Google is capable of retrieving a vast number of results, it struggles to access the deeper layers of digital repositories, meaning that many datasets remain unindexed and effectively invisible to standard web searches. This is because digital archives and institutional databases often operate within their own dedicated websites or online catalogues, each with its own unique search interface, metadata structure, and retrieval mechanisms. As a result, researchers must navigate multiple platforms individually, using different search tools and criteria, which significantly increases the time and effort required to locate relevant data.

Searching for a specific set of resources depends on how they are described and structured within the chosen data model. In the case of religious texts from the Nile Valley broad region, as focus of ReTINA, the search of resources become tricky, because it is necessary to identify texts with religious content and found or produced in a specific region of the world. Furthermore, because of the extension of the geographical area that includes many places and cultures, it is not possible to obtain results by using obviously a single definition such as "Nile Valley", unless the archive is not focused on this region as in the case of Trismegistos or one of the specific area or culture as the case of the Museo Egizio of Turin. In that case it needs to filter the results using the options available among the search functions. With respect to the identification of the geographical area "Nile Valley," which can be divided into different areas with different designations, such as Egypt, Upper Egypt, Lower Egypt, Nubia, or simply the name of a site, regarding the religious characteristics of the data, in some cases, the filter "Subject" includes the term "religious". However, the classification of these materials largely depends on how they have been categorized and, more importantly, on the criteria used to define what is considered religious. This is particularly significant when dealing with ancient objects, as the concept of religion in past societies often differed greatly from contemporary understandings. In modern times, religion is generally perceived as a structured system of beliefs, rituals, and practices centered around the divine or the spiritual realm. However, in ancient cultures, spiritual and religious elements were often deeply intertwined with other aspects of daily life, such as governance, magic, medicine, and even economic activities. This fluid and multifaceted nature of religious expression in the past makes it challenging to establish rigid classifications, as objects that served a ritualistic or sacred function may not always be explicitly identified as religious by modern standards. In the ITSERR project, many WPs focus on texts that refer to major religions, where the religious aspect is more evident. In contrast, in ancient times, religion was deeply integrated with multiple aspects of life. This results in the difficulty of attributing a religious or purely religious value to an object, even if it is inscribed and its text is translated. For example, in the case of the WP10 datasets, identifying the religious significance of an Ethiopian manuscript dedicated to the life of a saint is relatively straightforward, as the content explicitly relates to hagiography, devotion, and spiritual narratives. In contrast, recognizing the religious dimension of other artifacts can be more complex. An inscription on a bowl with magic/apotropaic/therapeutic

function, for instance, may not immediately appear as a religious text, even though such objects were often used in rituals, blessings, or healing practices rooted in spiritual traditions. Similarly, a text inscribed on a statue depicting both a ruler and a deity blurs the boundaries between political authority and divine representation, reflecting belief systems in which rulers were considered sacred or semi-divine figures. These examples illustrate how religious significance can be embedded in objects that, at first glance, may not be categorized as strictly religious according to modern classifications. The challenge, therefore, lies in developing interpretative frameworks that account for the cultural and historical context in which these objects were created and used. Moreover, in archaeology, the significance, function, and value of an object are deeply influenced by the context in which it was discovered and by its relationship with other associated objects. The spatial, cultural, and chronological framework in which an artifact is found can provide crucial insights into its original purpose, usage, and symbolic meaning. Objects recovered from ritual deposits, tombs, or sacred spaces, for example, may hold different connotations compared to those unearthed in everyday domestic settings, even if their physical characteristics appear similar. Additionally, the presence of related artifacts—such as inscriptions, offerings, or accompanying items—can further refine interpretations by indicating whether an object was used in religious ceremonies, administrative functions, or personal devotion.

This essential role of context was evident in the analysis of datasets, particularly in how different types of textual materials have been processed and managed. The study highlighted significant differences in the classification and handling of texts inscribed on archaeological artifacts compared to those contained in manuscripts. While manuscripts are typically preserved in structured collections with established cataloging systems, inscriptions on artifacts often require a more complex approach due to their fragmentary nature, physical medium, and direct connection to their findspot. These variations underscore the need for tailored methodologies when documenting, digitizing, and integrating textual data from diverse archaeological contexts

3.1 Data

According to the goal of this deliverable, one of the first steps for proposing a data model is to identify data requirements, and particularly the domain of digital data in a semantic perspective. For these reasons, two main aspects are important:

- ✓ the typology of data format
- ✓ and the content of the digital data.

The survey reveals that the published data encompasses a variety of formats, including visual representations such as images in TIFF and JPG formats, textual documents in formats like DOC and PDF, structured data stored in databases such as CSV and Excel files, as well as metadata organized in standardized formats like XML and JSON. These different

types of data provide diverse forms of information, ranging from visual depictions and written content to more technical datasets, each playing a vital role in documenting and analyzing the relevant materials. From a content perspective, the resources includes archaeological inscribed artifacts and historical documents, including books and manuscripts.

Both archaeological artifacts and historical documents are defined by an object that supports the text and by the text itself, which conveys the symbolic content. This text imbues the object with specific meaning within a particular context of use. The digital infrastructure ARIADNE⁴ which collects two million archaeological datasets and four million digital resources, and enables registration, aggregation, integration, search and retrieval of data records, does not distinguish between the object as a physical support and the text. Based on our survey, using ARIADNE to search for objects with associated texts from our region of interest proved challenging. As a result, we excluded ARIADNE from the initial survey. However, since this digital infrastructure is built on the concept of data integration, where the metadata of datasets are aggregated, maintained, and controlled by their respective owners, we decided to include it in the second phase of our investigation. The ARIADNE project has also focused on integrating archaeological data, which aligns closely with the objectives of ReTINA.

This digital infrastructure along with DARIAH⁵ and CLARIN⁶ have developed specific data models for the semantic organization of their resources according to the typology of their data which represent different disciplines such as archaeology and linguistics. In our case, the objective of RESILIENCE, and particularly of WP10 within ITSERR is to structure resources that encompass multiple disciplines - archaeology, philology, and linguistics - based on their religious content.

Analysing the content of the digital archive and how the information is managed, the archaeological objects and the historical documents are described differently due to the distinct procedures of discovery and preservation. However, the description primarily focuses on technical details related to the object, its provenance and preservation. The text, as an entity, has a close relationship with the object that supports it.

The portal DASI⁷ resolves the challenge of representing both the textual and material aspects of inscribed artifacts by structuring data into two interrelated entities: "Epigraph" and "Object" (Avanzini et al. 2014). This approach ensures that inscriptions are not only

⁴ <https://www.ariadne-research-infrastructure.eu/>)

⁵ <https://www.dariah.eu/>)

⁶ <https://www.clarin.eu/>)

⁷ <https://dasi.cnr.it/>

linked to their physical supports but also documented with relevant metadata, images, and bibliographic references.

By adopting this model, DASI overcomes the limitations of traditional paper editions, which often separate textual content from its material context. Unlike some digital projects that rely solely on databases, DASI enhances text accessibility through advanced search functions and contributes to the development of a lexicon for South Arabian languages. The "Epigraph" entity organizes data related to script, language, chronology, and text type, while also including general and cultural annotations beyond standard critical notes.

At the same time, DASI preserves the autonomy of object-related data. Rather than embedding it within the textual attributes, the "Object" entity maintains a direct link to inscriptions while documenting key aspects such as material, dimensions, provenance, archaeological context, and decorative elements. This structured approach allows for a more integrated and flexible exploration of inscribed artifacts, combining textual and material dimensions in a coherent framework.

Figure 1 Datatype published by digital archives

Analyzing the digital archives, a significant methodological difference emerges in the cataloging of textual documents based on their material support. This distinction reveals different disciplinary approaches that profoundly influence classification and metadata systems.

When it comes to historical documents, such as manuscripts, descriptive attention primarily focuses on the textual content. Descriptive records favor information such as the

author, title, dating, and content analysis, while the material aspects of the medium take on a secondary role. The manuscript is essentially conceived as a vehicle for the text, and its importance lies mainly in the information it transmits.

In contrast, when text appears on an archaeological object, there is a reversal of descriptive priorities. Descriptive metadata is predominantly focused on the physical object: material, dimensions, context of discovery, original function, and state of preservation. The inscription on the object is often relegated to accessory information and, in some extreme cases, may not even be mentioned in the main descriptive record.

This methodological divergence reflects not only different disciplinary traditions between archival science and archaeology but also raises questions about the effectiveness of our documentation systems and the need for a more integrated approach. The clear separation between textual content and material support risks generating significant information losses, compromising the global understanding of the documents and objects that constitute our cultural heritage. This is particularly evident on museum websites that feature large and diverse collections. Unlike repositories for historical documents, which focus primarily on preserving textual content, museum digital archives serve a dual purpose: safeguarding information and showcasing the richness of their collections. Since museums are perceived as places dedicated to the preservation of physical objects, their digital archives are designed to reflect the structure of the actual museum. As a result, it is challenging to develop repositories that offer in-depth analyses of the collections.

In contrast, repositories realized for specific projects and focused on specific classes of textual objects such as the Database of Medieval Nubian texts⁸, DASI⁹, Path¹⁰, and others, often provide detailed descriptions of the text and, in many cases, the text itself. The observed trend involves registering the text with a persistent identifier, linked to key information such as technical details about the support, place of discovery and preservation, text typology, and language. However, it is rare to find repositories where all texts are fully transcribed; more commonly, an image is provided alongside metadata. However, the image alone is readable only by humans and not by machines unless processed with recognition systems.

Each digital archive structures its data based on specific needs. What matters is the trend observed in the use of metadata standards, as highlighted in D10.1. The survey indicates that the metadata standards adopted in digital archives are among the most widely recognized and commonly used today. However, as discussed in D10.1, a single standard is not necessarily adopted. Instead, there is a tendency to develop data models that integrate

⁸ <https://www.dbmnt.uw.edu.pl/>

⁹ <https://dasi.cnr.it/>

¹⁰ <http://paths.uniroma1.it/>

multiple standards, allowing for a more accurate representation of the dataset and its contents. Examples include Arachne¹¹, which employs CIDOC-CRM, METS, MODS, and TEI, and Beta Masaheft¹², which combines CIDOC-CRM and TEI. Indeed, the needs of representing an archaeological artefact with text are different for archaeologists and epigraphists: the first consider the artifact itself and its context as the subject of its studies, the second consider the artifact as a support for the text that will be the focus. Therefore, both, archaeologists and epigraphists, use different data models.

4 Interoperability and Mapping

The creation of many digital archives has raised the key issue of interoperability, which requires a considerable effort in terms of organization and standardization¹³. To enhance the interoperability of digital archives, it is essential to connect datasets organized according to different data models, which makes it challenging to integrate and share information across platforms.

A data model is a structured representation of the information and relationships within the archive's dataset. It can be defined as a framework that specifies the structure, semantics, and relationships of metadata elements used to describe data objects within a digital archive. The goal of a data model is to provide a standardized and interoperable framework for creating, managing, and exchanging metadata across heterogeneous digital archives and systems. The common use of more metadata standards and vocabularies enhances interoperability and data integration.

Therefore, one of the objectives of D10.2 was to provide a conceptual framework for the alignment of descriptive schemas used in different datasets with a common standard or model, enabling interoperability. The process of metadata mapping ensures that datasets from diverse sources can be aggregated and accessed more easily, allowing for more efficient data sharing, searching, and analysis across digital archives and platforms. In this way, researchers who wish to aggregate their own datasets into a platform need to map the local metadata system used to describe the data to the schema adopted by the community managing the platform.

This process consists of three levels:

¹¹ <https://arachne.dainst.org/>

¹² <https://www.betamasaheft.uni-hamburg.de/>

¹³ On the topic see, for example, Castelli, Felicetti, Proietti 2021

- ✓ the bottom level includes datasets that may be organized as structured databases or in unstructured formats, such as texts on websites or blogs. At this level, the data remains isolated and cannot be easily combined or queried together.
- ✓ The second level involves mapping and standardization. The first step toward integration is mapping the various metadata schemas used in local datasets to a common schema. This process requires aligning the fields and descriptions of each local dataset with a widely accepted standard within the community or target platform. Standardization is essential to ensure interoperability between datasets with different structures.
- ✓ The third and upper level is aggregation. Once metadata mapping is completed, datasets can be aggregated into a common platform or infrastructure.

This infrastructure provides a structured system that integrates data from diverse sources, allowing users to consistently search, access, and analyze the information. At this level, the infrastructure manages homogeneous data that follows shared standards, making it findable and accessible through search tools and other applications. Once aggregated, datasets not only become interoperable but can also be enriched through further linkages and integration with other data sources. These connections enable more complex interactions between datasets, increasing analytical possibilities and facilitating new discoveries by linking information across different communities or domains.

Figure 2 Process for data aggregation

4.1 Standards

Based on the survey, the declared standards that form the foundation of the data models in the analyzed digital archives are described. According to paragraph 1.5.3 of Deliverable 10.1, out of 40 digital archives, we only found information for 17 digital collections. This indicates that some of the consulted archives may use standards that were not easily identifiable. The table below presents the main standards used for representing digital collections.

LINE ¹⁴	TITLE	Standards	VOCABULARIES
4	MuseiD-Italia	METS, Pico, VRA Core, PREMIS	
5	Corpus of Ptolemaic Inscriptions	EpiDoc	Trismegistos
6	Musem	LIDO	
7	Papyri.info	TEI, EpiDoc	PeriodO, AAT
8	PATHs	TEI	
9	Mummy Label Database	TEI, EpiDoc	
10	Corpus Louvre	CIDOC-CRM	
11	Ancient World Digital Library	KBART-metadata, DCMI, MODS	
12	Arachne	CIDOC-CRM, METS, MODS, TEI	
15	DASI	TEI, EpiDoc, Dublin Core, EDM	
17	Propylaeum	CIDOC-CRM, TEI	GND, Getty
23	Beta Masaheft	CIDOC-CRM, TEI	Pleaiades, Trismegistos, PeriodO, EAGLE vocabularies, GODOT
27	British Museum	CIDOC-CRM	British Museum thesauri
29	Die Aegyptiaca der Universität Göttingen im Sammlungsportal	LIDO	Iconclass, Geonames, DNB, GVK, Wikipedia
32	The Walters Art Museum	Dublin Core, TEI	

¹⁴ The number of line is referred to the line in the table 1 of D10.1

36	University Cambridge Digital Library	METS, MODS, TEI
37	The Metropolitan Museum of Arts	CIDOC-CRM, CIDOC CRMdig, Nomisma, Dublin Core

Table 1 Overview of the data standards and vocabularies in the analyzed digital archives. As per paragraph 1.5.3 of Deliverable 10.1, information was found for 17 out of 40 collections, indicating that some archives may use less identifiable standards.

The adopted data models include standards as CIDOC-CRM, Dublin Core, TEI, EpiDoc, METS, MODS, LIDO and obsolete structure as PICO (application profile del DC) that is a standard used only by the Italian project of CulturalItalia and MuseiD-Italia. CIDOC-CRM, Dublin Core, METS, MODS and LIDO are all standards used in the cultural heritage and digital library communities. They describe the resources from the digital and physical perspective, but they serve different purposes and focus on different aspects of metadata and data management. Among them, CIDOC-CRM is considered a domain ontology which deals with the formal representation of knowledge within the domain of cultural heritage, defining concepts and relationships, while the other structures here listed are metadata which focuses on describing specific instances of data or resources to facilitate their discovery and management. Ontologies provide the conceptual framework for organizing and interpreting metadata within a domain.

Given the wide availability of standards and their established use in many European cultural institutions, D10.2 briefly describes the most widely used data-models that are particularly useful for semantic enrichment of datasets.

Here, we summarize the scope and use of main data models used in Cultural Heritage.

CIDOC-CRM (Conceptual Reference Model):

- **Scope:** CIDOC-CRM provides a conceptual framework for organizing and describing cultural heritage information, focusing on semantic interoperability between different cultural heritage data sources. It emphasizes the representation of cultural heritage objects, events, and their relationships in a formalized way, enabling consistent and comprehensive description and interpretation of cultural heritage data.
- **Use:** CIDOC-CRM is used for modelling complex relationships and concepts within cultural heritage collections, supporting interoperability between different cultural heritage databases and systems.
<https://cidoc-crm.org/>

Dublin Core:

- Scope: Dublin Core is a simple and widely used metadata standard for describing digital resources on the web. It provides a basic set of elements for describing resources, such as title, creator, subject, description, publisher, date, etc., in a way that is easy to understand and implement.
- Use: Dublin Core is commonly used for basic resource description in various contexts, including digital libraries, archives, and museums, where detailed metadata may not be required.
<https://www.dublincore.org/>

METS (Metadata Encoding and Transmission Standard):

- Scope: METS provides a standard format for encoding metadata, digital content, and structural information within digital library objects. It focuses on packaging digital objects and their associated metadata in a structured way, facilitating interoperability and exchange between different digital library systems.
- Use: METS is commonly used to package digital objects along with descriptive, administrative, and structural metadata in a single XML file, supporting the management and dissemination of digital collections.
<https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>

MODS (Metadata Object Description Schema):

- Scope: MODS is a metadata schema developed by the Library of Congress for describing bibliographic metadata for digital resources. It provides a more detailed and structured set of elements for describing digital resources, including title, author, subject, date, format, etc., in a machine-readable XML format.
- Use: MODS is often used alongside METS to provide detailed descriptive metadata for digital objects within a METS package, supporting more granular description and discovery of digital resources.
<https://www.loc.gov/standards/mets/>

LIDO (Lightweight Information Describing Objects):

- Scope: LIDO is a metadata standard for describing cultural heritage objects, particularly works of art and museum objects. It provides a structured framework for encoding descriptive, administrative, and technical metadata about cultural objects. LIDO focuses on providing a set of elements and guidelines for describing the essential information about cultural objects, including titles, creators, dates, materials, dimensions, and rights information.

- Use: It is used by museums, galleries, and other cultural heritage institutions for cataloguing, documenting, and sharing information about their collections.

<https://cidoc.mini.icom.museum/working-groups/lido/lido-overview/>

The other standards are TEI and EpiDoc. Both are markup languages used for encoding and representing texts, particularly in the context of digital humanities and scholarly research. In particular, TEI is the most widely adopted in projects focused on collecting textual materials. According to our research, the only museum that use it is the Walter Art Museum. However, we cannot exclude the possibility that other museums do not adopt this standard. Indeed, of 40 digital archives, information is not available for seventeen, while six do not use any standards.

TEI (Text Encoding Initiative):

- Scope: TEI is a standard markup language designed for encoding and representing texts in digital form. It provides a set of guidelines and recommendations for encoding various aspects of textual documents, including structural, linguistic, and bibliographic features. It covers a wide range of textual materials, including literary works, historical documents, manuscripts, and linguistic corpora. It allows scholars and researchers to encode and annotate texts with rich metadata, annotations, and structural elements to support analysis, interpretation, and dissemination.
- Use: TEI is widely used in the digital humanities, libraries, archives, and scholarly publishing. It enables the creation of digital editions, textual corpora, and scholarly resources that are interoperable, searchable, and reusable.

<https://tei-c.org/>

EpiDoc:

- Scope: EpiDoc is a specialized markup language based on TEI specifically designed for encoding inscriptions and other written documents from the ancient world, particularly those in Greek and Latin. EpiDoc focuses on encoding the specific features and characteristics of epigraphic texts, such as inscriptions, graffiti, and other written artifacts. It provides a set of guidelines and schemas for representing the content, layout, and metadata of epigraphic texts allowing to annotate linguistic (onomastic and grammatical) and philological (restorations, corrections, lacunae..) phenomena, the critical notes, the internal structures of the texts and the relation between the object as support and the texts (such as the position of the text and the epigraphic panel). Furthermore, it allows to the images and drawing of the epigraphic artifact to be described.

- Use: EpiDoc is used by scholars, archaeologists, and epigraphers to create digital editions of inscriptions, cataloguing databases, and scholarly publications. It enables the encoding and dissemination of epigraphic texts in digital form, allowing for collaborative research, analysis, and interpretation.

<https://epidoc.stoa.org/>

These standards have inspired or are at the base of the conceptualization of other data models used by the Cultural Heritage community which were created with aims of aggregate datasets from different domains or for a specific one. This is the case of EDM, AO-CAT, and EAGLE.

5 Data Integration

In data aggregation process, a common practice is to identify an agreed data model for aggregating metadata used by different Content Providers that allows to deal with the data heterogeneity between organizations and countries in a sustainable way. These data models typically aim to retain the semantics of the original data from the source providers, and to support the information needs of the services provided by the aggregator. Data models can answer to needs of a different levels and range of domains. Its level of development varies across domains and uses cases. In order to identify a data model that suite to the aggregation of dataset which will be part of ReTINA as component of Resilience, we took into consideration different experiences gained in Cultural Heritage domain:

- Europeana Data Model used for representing datasets related to the Cultural Heritage;
- EAGLE focused on the datasets containing epigraphic material and CIDOC-CRMtex and extension of CIDOC-CRM provided with classes and properties for the description of epigraphic data;
- AO-Cat used for aggregating archaeological datasets by the ARIADNEplus infrastructure;
- Schema.org that covers a wide range of domain is a potential technology for metadata aggregation in the Cultural Heritage domain.
- CIDOC-CRMtex which includes both descriptions of the supports and the texts that carry.

5.1 Europeana Data Model (EDM)

Launched in 2008, Europeana¹⁵, the digital platform that gives integrated access to millions of digitized cultural resources from Europe's museums, libraries, archives, and audiovisual collections aims at facilitating the discovery, sharing, and use of European cultural heritage material by making it available online. It seeks to enable users to access knowledge either directly, via the web portal, or indirectly, via third-party applications built on top of its data service. Europeana is based on the aggregation and exploitation of (meta)data from very different contexts developing infrastructures and workflows for aggregating, ingesting, indexing, normalising, and publishing. It aggregates digital representations of cultural heritage items, offering a central access point for collections from thousands of European cultural institutions. Datasets from diverse sources to be integrated seamlessly, are described by means of standards like the Europeana Data Model (EDM), which is designed to support interoperability and enrich metadata¹⁶. The Europeana Data Model is a major improvement on the Europeana Semantic Elements (ESE), the basic data model that Europeana began life with. As each of the different heritage sectors represented in Europeana uses different data standards, ESE was the first system used to Europeana for reducing these to the lowest common denominator. EDM reverses the ESE reductive approach and is an attempt to transcend the respective information perspectives of the sectors that are represented in Europeana. It adopts an open, cross-domain Semantic Web-based framework that can accommodate the range and richness of community standards. Indeed, it adheres to the modelling principles that underpin the approach of the Web of Data. It means that there is not a fixed schema that guides the representation of data, but just one way to do it allowing to anchor various finer-grained models without requiring to local providers significant change to their systems.

The main goal is to standardize representation of heterogeneous records. It separates the description of the cultural heritage object from its digital representation. To enable this separation, it defines two classes: `edm:ProvidedCHO`, `edm:WebResource`¹⁷.

¹⁵ <https://www.europeana.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

¹⁷ Europeana data-model guidelines v.2.4 <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

Figure 3 The three core classes of EDM. Europeana data-Model guidelines v.2.4, p.6 (<https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>)

The term ProvidedCHO refers to a cultural heritage object which has given rise to and is the subject of the package of data that has been submitted to Europeana. Thus, the first describes the original objects— either physical (e.g. a painting, a book, museum objects, and archival documents etc.) or born-digital (e.g. a 3D model) which are expected to be the focus of users' interest and search in Europeana. The second class describes the digital representation of the provided cultural heritage object which is the element manipulated in information systems like Europeana, publishing the resource on the Web. For demonstrating that the provided object and the digital representation is a logical whole, the core structure of EDM includes a third class: ore:Aggregation. It is the pivotal object between the edm:ProvidedCHO and the edm:WebResource(s) because groups the instances of both classes recording the information on the aggregation process. Each instance of ore:Aggregation is related to one resource that stands for the provided object, and one or more resources that are digital representations of the provided object, representing the fact that the aggregation indeed aggregates the "real" object and its digital views. The class serves as an organizing construct for creating perspectives on CHOs ("proxies") that carry provider-specific data on these objects, thus allowing one to separate it from data on the same object from other providers (including Europeana). Since Europeana takes data from many providers, this data may be about the same real-world resource giving different views on the same resource. The resources are described with different metadata. For guarantying the many views of the same resource, Europeana uses the edm:Proxy class and its properties to enable the representation of resources in the context of aggregations.

The instances of these classes are related by means of specific properties.

The objects provided to Europeana need to be described and contextualized. To support the modeling of such semantic enrichment and to support further enrichment, EDM features a number of classes devoted to the representation of "contextual" entities:

- edm:Agent, to be used for representing persons or organizations

- edm:Event, for events
- edm:Place, for spatial entities
- edm:TimeSpan, for time periods or dates
- skos:Concept, for all entities from knowledge organization systems like thesauri, classification schemes.

These classes are used to link objects to other resources (concepts, places, persons...) related to them¹⁸. EDM allows two approaches for capturing the different features of a resource as well as relates it to the other entities in its context: the object-oriented approach and the event-oriented approach. The first approach is based on metadata that provides a direct linking between the described object and its features. Most of them are from Dublin Core metadata set. In this approach the dc: and dcterms: properties can be used to directly link text values to the object. Some of the values in the descriptive metadata can be seen to be related not to the object but to another resource in the description captured in EDM by using an entity. The event-centric approach considers that descriptions of objects should focus on characterizing the various events in which objects have been involved. This approach underlies models such CIDOC-CRM. The class edm:Events is now the "hub" that relates the object to other entities that were directly connected to it in the previous object-centric approach. These relations are represented in EDM using the three following properties:

- edm:wasPresentAt, holding between any resource and an event it is involved in;
- edm:happenedAt, holding between an event and a place;
- edm:occurredAt, holding between events and the time spans during which they occurred.

Although the simple structure allows one to be able to describe the resources by providing the main descriptions, EDM supports the retention of complete item descriptions from data providers. On the webpage of the resources of Europeana there is the possibility to access the webpage of the provider by means of the landing page.

The structure of EDM allows the description of complex objects, such as archives or digitized books, that are in common the division in sections, EDM supports these types of resources that can be understood both individually and collectively. In particular, archives are usually described using EAD (Encoding Archival Description) files, which can represent hierarchical containment between different "levels" of archive resources. Hierarchies of

¹⁸ See the example in Europeana data-model guidelines v.2.4, p.43, <https://pro.europeana.eu/page/edm-documentation>

objects are common also in the case of manuscript or book that on one side is considered as a physical unit and its contents is addressing to one general concept, on the other side is considered as a grouping of individual pages, each of them being digitized and potentially answering a user's information need.

5.2 Description of archaeological data, the case of AO-Cat

The ontology AO-Cat was developed within the ARIADNEplus project. ARIADNEplus goes on through ARIADNE Research Infrastructure. AISBL is a digital infrastructure and services that enable registration, aggregation, integration, search and retrieval of data records which describe and link to the available data(sets). Its main objective is to support research, learning and teaching by enabling access to digital resources and innovative new services. It does this by maintaining a catalogue of digital datasets, by promoting best practices in the management and use of digital data in archaeology, by offering training and advice, and by supporting the development of innovative new services for archaeology. At present, about three million data have been catalogued, corresponding to a huge amount of information as each dataset may comprise.

The catalogued content types range from individual finds to monuments and sites inventories and from the report of one single intervention to the results of a long-term archaeological mission.

Figure 4 Schema for the description of archaeological data in the AO-Cat ontology

Data are not aggregated in ARIADNE but the metadata of the datasets, which are maintained and controlled by their owners. According to the two basic requirements, enabling cross-border/cross-institution resource discovery, i.e. finding data; enabling interoperability—across partners, countries, data types, data schemas, i.e. enabling research, the ARIADNE Catalogue (AC) is expected to store information about digital objects belonging to a large range of data types, forming a heterogeneous set, as data is diverse in character and content. In addition, different levels of granularity must be accounted for, supporting collection and item level interoperability, e.g., sites and the individual artefacts they contain.

The metadata in the Catalogue have originated from many different sources with varying levels of information and data models. ARIADNE has developed AO-CAT that is a formal ontology of the resources managed by a research infrastructure, with a special focus on the archaeological domain and on its infrastructure.

AO-Cat derives from the ARIADNE Catalogue Data Model (ACDM for short), employed in the predecessor ARIADNE project to model archaeological resources, and from the PARTHENOS Entities Model (PEM), employed in the PARTHENOS project to model the resources managed by a research infrastructure. In addition, it inherits from the PEM its tight relation to the CRM, which is used to represent any aspect of archaeological resources. Indeed, the ontology inherits the CIDOC-CRM model and philosophy to provide the community with a powerful and efficient integration tool, capable of capturing the

meaning of a diverse range of archaeological data sets offered by content providers and integrating their data in a unique and coherent way. The aim is to present a core ontology to which data providers map their individual database schema, thereby ensuring interoperability between diverse resources. It is capable of being deployed at the “site” or “monument” level, but it can also be effectively implemented at item level, e.g. for individual artefacts or graves. For ARIADNE a resource is a web resource, therefore it is identified with an HTTP IRI (Internationalized Resource Identifier) in the ARIADNE domain, and it is described defining the typology and using other proprieties which can refer to the creation, modification, ownership, responsibilities and so on. The web resource refers to a data resource that is described in AO-CAT by using the subclasses of AO_Data_Resources: AO_Individuals and AO_Collections. The class AO_Collections is interesting because it refers to the aggregation of resources which are the members in the collections and as consequence they can have other collections as members. Similarly, the archive can contain different objects like reports, collection of images, database. Otherwise, the AO_Individuals contains atomic instances that cannot be divided into other resources.

A web resource can be described by using a number of properties which specify the creation, extent, landing page, policy, rights and language, and so on, but it can relate to the entity to which it refers to or it is about. This connection realized with properties and ARIADNE fundamental categories or the terms of the Getty Art & Architecture Thesaurus (AAT)¹⁹ is useful for describing the topicality required to support the *What* searches in the portal. In addition to this, the resource is associated to spatial and temporal region to support the *Where* and *When* searches. For contextualizing the digital resource in ARIADNE infrastructure is important the class AO_Object that defines all the physical objects and includes three properties that connect the instances of the class with the space, time and the event. The generic class AO_Spatial_Region has two properties that indicate the coordinates and the place names. However, the sub-classe of AO_Spatial_Region allows to describe the place as points (longitude and latitude), polygons represented in some format typically managed by a GIS, bounded boxes and standard names in specific vocabularies indicating the IRI. About time, AO-CAT faced the problem related to the different representation of time in the archaeological domain, often associated with space or culture. AO-Cat supports the absolute dates with respect to a reference system and time interval with a beginning and end. Moreover, it supports time intervals indicated by name such as “Neolithic”, even if they need to be connected to a standard vocabulary. AO-Cat relies on the PeriodO gazetteer service²⁰.

¹⁹ <https://www.getty.edu/research/tools/vocabularies/aat/>

²⁰ <https://perio.do/en/>

PeriodO allows the definition of a temporal interval as a web resource, associated with a label and a pair of absolute dates. Events and activities play an important role in contextualising the data resources held by ARIADNE. AO-Cat follows the conceptual structure of the CRM, where an event is a “change of states in cultural, social or physical systems, regardless of scale, brought about by a series or group of coherent physical, cultural, technological or legal phenomena” [CIDOC-CRM Specs 6.2]. The classes AO_Event and AO_Activity may describe the activities concern the archaeological research, the physical object and the digital object. They can be long-lasting or short-lived actions. It is possible to document in the case of a collection, which is a composite data resource, a single activity, while the members of the collection may document parts of that activity. Thus, an event connected to the collection can contain multiple events produced by different agents. Indeed, as in the case of CIDOC-CRM, AO-Cat models entities that can act, and they are distinguished in persons and organizations by using the two subclasses AO_Person and AO_Group. They carry out activities, hold various responsibilities for the resources and for making resources available and publicly accessible.

Figure 5 Entities and relationships in archaeological domain (Felicetti A. et al., 2023, p.11)

According to Felicetti et al. (2023) the basic pattern in archaeological modeling is characterized by the event instance of the class AO_Event. These instances relate to the instance of AO_Object, site/monument with the property was_present_at, and the relation between the instance of AO_Data_Resource like archive, and the event is represented with the property is_about. It is demonstrated by the figure the modeling is inspired by the CIDOC-CRM. The AO_Cat application profile is characterized by some extensions that try to capture different aspects of resources, especially archaeological activities, by using the CRMdig or Dublin Core.

About the description of texts such as manuscripts and inscriptions ARIADNE has taken into consideration some models already used by ARIADNE partners, among them there is CRMtex. It is an extension of CIDOC-CRM created to support the study of ancient documents by identifying relevant textual entities and by modeling the scientific process related with the investigation of ancient texts and their features in order to foster integration with other cultural heritage research fields, such as archaeology and history. The extension introduces new classes and properties more responsive to the specific needs of the various disciplines, papyrology, paleography, codicology and epigraphy. On the webpage <https://cidoc-crm.org/crmtext/> it is noted that is a work in progress. Another initiative is EAGLE project. EAGLE has developed a CIDOC-CRM compatible metadata model with a complete set of extremely useful vocabularies for describing epigraphic entities.

5.3 Description of inscription, the case of EAGLE

EAGLE project aims at aggregating epigraphic databases from various content providers partners and uses them by means of the EAGLE Portal²¹. Therefore, EAGLE project has defined a conceptual model that all content providers can use to map their own data,

Figure 6 Descriptive elements of epigraphic material (Sicilia M.A. et al. 2015, p.11)

generally described with different models, for ingesting in Europeana. The core of the EAGLE data model is based on the dual aspect of the datasets: the physical object and the text supported by it. The conceptual model and the schema developed for EAGLE are based on TEI/EpiDoc that is able to guarantee easy mapping to the CIDOC-CRM. TEI/EpiDoc is a tool for encoding scholarly and educational editions of ancient documents and it allows a full description of the text of inscriptions. It addresses not only the transcription and editorial treatment of texts themselves, but also the history and materiality of the objects on which the texts appear. However, the descriptive part of the TEI/EpiDoc guidelines lacks the articulation and the potential of the CIDOC-CRM. Indeed,

²¹ <https://www.eagle-network.eu/eagle-project/documents-deliverables/>

CIDOC-CRM provides a formal ontological model for describing the structure of cultural heritage objects and the relationships between them, including event models for representing the life cycle of the objects. Moreover, it allows expression in RDF not only of elements and attributes but of entities and properties which relate to the different values. Moreover, URIs are introduced at every stage with the purpose to enrich and harmonize contents. This allows to face the challenge of restructuring Linked Open Data. About the identification of the resource, the EAGLE data model includes also information from one of the providers, Trismegistos.

Trismegistos provides a de-duplication service for minting stable unique identifiers to epigraphic documents. The indication of the Trismegistos ID is important when the same epigraph is being provided by more than one Content Providers for disambiguate and manage both the ingestion and the query results.

CIDOC-CRM is very well suited to describe the epigraph as a physical object and give an event-based description that focus on activities such as creation, finding and conservation of the object, being much more precise and unambiguous especially concerning the object itself. The description is not limited to the definition of the inscribed objects and texts but also to the contextualization of them indicating location, time and agents referred to specific events such as creation, finding, acquisition, preservation and curation of information, including interpretations and conjectures. In this way it is possible to get the best of both worlds and have a complete interoperable description of the epigraphic assets. In addition, the representation needs to cover different materializations of information about these artefacts, which includes replicas, images and any other kind of media that is bearing information about them.

In CIDOC-CRM, the object who bears the inscription is described as instance of the class E22 Man-Made Object, while the epigraphic field is an instance of the class E84 Information Carrier. This is related to the monument object using property P46i forms part of.

Figure 7 High-level model (Sicilia, M.A. et al. 2015, p. 12)

the epigraphic field, it has some characteristics difficult to specify with CIDOC-CRM such as the paleographic

aspects. For those, the model uses the property P3 has Note and the class as range E62 String. The information that is represented on the epigraphic field is described with the class E34 Inscription. Possible translations of the inscriptions are instances of E73

Information Object related with the inscriptions by means with the property P73 hasTranslation.

According to the characteristics of the two standards and the needs due to the epigraphic material, the main question is the description of the text and its content. For this reason, the two sets of standards CIDOC-CRM and TEI/EpidoC were used to create a mapping. The EAGLE metadata model, developed within the project consortium, has tried to map all content providers data to both these international standards, and has worked also towards a mapping among the two standards, based on the data of most of the major inscription databases.

Starting from these two data standards, the EAGLE Aggregation Metadata Schema has been defined and materialized into an XML Schema (.xsd file). It is used internally by the aggregator in the EAGLE server. The ingestion of the material supplied by Content Providers into EAGLE is implemented by the EAGLE aggregation infrastructure, and a mapping from the providers dataset and EAGLE has been defined. The EAGLE Aggregation Metadata Schema describes the format of the entities and properties identified in the model (D3.1). It focuses on a set of main entities for what concerns the requirements of the EAGLE portal, identifying a smaller and simpler subset of the CIDOC-CRM conceptual model, without losing any information about all the different facets of epigraphy-related data that will be aggregated in the EAGLE portal. The metadata format was defined in order to simplify queries. The resulting data model consists of a root entity (the EAGLE Object) from which five sub-entities can be derived, each one capturing some of the properties that have been identified thanks to the EpiDoc and CIDOC-CRM:

1. Trismegistos Card which consists of a TM ID, some properties and relationships related to instances of the same resource;
2. Artifact which jointly represents E22 Man-Made Object and E84 Information Carrier in CIDOC-CRM;
3. Inscription as an optional entity inside Artifact which describes the textual and semantic nature of the text. It corresponds to E34 Inscription in CIDOC-CRM;
4. Visual Representation which collects all the material related to the “visual nature” of the epigraph and can be relative either to born-digital photo and computer graphics or to digitized drawings and literature;
5. Documental Manifestation which contains all information related to the “textual nature” of an inscription. It has two subentities: Transcription and Translation. These two last sub entities, Transcription and Translation, with Trismegistos card and Visual representation represent different materializations of E33 Linguistic Object, E73 Information Object, and E38 Image in CIDOC-CRM.

Figure 8 Eagle aggregator conceptual model (Sicilia, M.A., 2015, p.46)

The five sub-entities share several common properties: Resource identifier which refers to the ID of the Eagle aggregation system; Provenance information related to the content providers; Metadata editing information which captures information about the creator of metadata contents and the modifications; Metadata intellectual property rights statement (IPR) referred to the copyright status of the resource; Title of the resource; Description; EAGLE object type.

One of the most important goals of EAGLE project is to provide epigraphic material to Europeana contributing to enabling digital access to epigraphic resources, not only for researchers but also for the general public. The advantage is that data coming from providers may be enhanced by the content from other providers or rich web sources, creating meaningful relations between items and translating the metadata at the same time. The digital epigraphic material that has to be ingested into Europeana needs to be mapped to the EDM. It effectively addresses the need to describe artifacts, which all content providers, even if using different schemas, generally represent in a similar way.

5.4 Schema.org

Schema.org is a markup language used by webmasters who want to improve the comprehension of the content of their webpages from the search engines by means of a better indexing of the content, providing detailed information and enhancing higher visibility of their webpage. It consists of common vocabulary shared by webmasters to markup their HTML content. The main search engines, such as Google, Bing, Yahoo! and Yandex, interpret the markup because Schema.org uses a language which describes the elements of the website. This is a different way to give the search engines additional information about any object contained on the site. When search engines identify meaning and relationship among the entity described by a common schema, they can return better search results and rich snippets. Schema.org has been developed according to the Semantic Web and Linked Data principles and it consists of an RDF graph. The vocabulary can be used with many different encodings, including RDFa, Microdata and JSON-LD. It

describes a variety of item types, each of which has its own set of properties that can be used to describe the item. The broadest item type is Thing, which has four properties: name, description, URL, and image. More specific types share properties with broader types. Thing includes the following types²²:

- Creative works
- Embedded non-text objects: AudioObject, ImageObject, VideoObject
- Event
- Organization
- Person
- Place, LocalBusiness, Restaurant...
- Product, Offer, AggregateOffer
- Review, AggregateRating

In the Cultural Heritage sector, since Europeana represents the main access point to a huge quantity of cultural heritage objects resulting from an aggregation process, it is important for Europeana to be identified as a trusted repository of cultural heritage on the web. Moreover, most of the Europeana users come to it via search engines, especially Google. Schema.org enables search engines in particular, to crawl and add data into their Knowledge Graphs, thus enhancing the discoverability of resources. For this reason, Europeana started to research the benefits of Schema.org²³.

As the provided cultural heritage object is represented into the Europeana Data Model, a set of data mapping recommendations has been established.

The Schema.org approach is to define schema:CreativeWork, which allows the description of books, maps, visual art, music recordings, and many other kinds of cultural resources, equivalent to the edm:ProvidedCHO plus links to access the resource. In EDM the type of object is defined via properties such as dc:type referred to concepts from the Getty Arts and Architecture thesaurus, in the case of Schema.org it is preferable wherever possible to identify the type of thing being described schema:Book, schema:Painting, schema:Sculpture, schema:ImageObject etc.

The same is the case of the mapping among edm:WebResources and schema:MediaObject where the type should be described using the most specific subclasses such as schema:ImageObject, schema:AudioObject, schema:VideoObject.

The *ore:Aggregation* class required in EDM has not equivalent in Schema.org. However, even *edm:type* and *edm:rights* have not a direct equivalent. For *edm:type* it is possible to refer to the subclasses of schema:CreativeWork, while regarding *edm:rights*, Schema.org

²² <https://schema.org/docs/schemas.html>

²³ <https://journal.code4lib.org/articles/12330>

does contain properties such as schema:license that can be suitable vehicles for the values requested by EDM. However, while Schema.org does not restrict the values for schema:license, EDM expects rights statements from Creative Commons and RightsStatements.org (Freire et al. 2018).

About the classes that describe the contexts, schema:Person, schema:Place and schema:Organization match the semantics of EDM contextual classes edm:Agent, edm:Place and foaf:Organization

The mechanism to aggregate Schema.org data can start the same way as for crawling ordinary web pages. Crawling is the process whereby search engines and other applications systematically explore the web to collect data. Schema.org was created for indexing the webpages through a structured and coded system that can be easily interpreted by search engines. The use of a shared structured Metadata standard aims to extract and use structured metadata to improve the indexing and presentation of information. Thus, unlike general crawling, which analyzes the entire textual content of a web page, Schema.org data crawling focuses on structured metadata. Usually, webmasters may aid the web crawling process by providing Sitemaps of their website, which are files that list the pages of a Web site to inform search engines about the structure of the site.

Sitemaps allow web crawlers to reach areas of the website that are not available through the browsable interface. Moreover, sitemaps can be useful also in the case of Cultural Heritage institutions websites, where the number of objects varies over time as collections grow, and there is a possibility that web crawlers will overlook some of the new or recently updated content.

5.5 Integrating text and supports: CIDOC-CRMtex²⁴

CRMtex was developed from the EAGLE experience and is the result of collaboration among scholars from numerous cultural heritage institutions. It was created to support the study of ancient, inscribed documents, with the primary goal of enhancing the integration and interoperability of data related to ancient texts at every level. This includes the description of the supports and the texts they carry, as well as the management of documentation produced by various institutions following national and institutional standards (e.g., TEI/EpiDoc). Moreover, CRMtex advocates for the use of the CIDOC-CRM model to encode documents and represent the scientific investigation process, thereby facilitating integration across different research fields. As an extension of CIDOC-CRM, CRMtex is based on the premise that text and its support form a single object of study, being intrinsically connected. CRMtex is structured around 14 classes (TX) and 18 properties (TXP), which are designed to describe and identify the key entities involved in the study and

²⁴ https://cidoc-crm.org/crmtex/fm_releases

editing of ancient handwritten texts, such as inscriptions, papyri, manuscripts, and similar supports²⁵. The model is designed to describe the phenomena from creation (and/or destruction) of the texts, down to the conservation, investigation and studies conducted by scholars, including transcription, translation, interpretation and publication. Moreover, being an extension, takes advantage of CIDOC-CRM and its other extensions to describe general non-textual information (i.e., actors, places, objects, temporal entities, observations, archaeological contexts and so forth).

The digitisation of the handwritten texts has to consider the methods and technique of many different disciplines such as papyrology, epigraphy, paleography and so on. Therefore, the approach used for the elaboration of the model was characterized by an interdisciplinary approach identifying elements common to different disciplines. The first aspect is the close relationship between the text and the support. The link between the text and the physical object is realized through the class TX1 WritingWritten Text that is a subclass of CIDOC-CRM E25 Human-Made Feature, and describes the text on a support, it means the physical signs that make up a text on a physical support. An example of TX1 is the signs composing the inscription engraved on various parts of the magic bowls (E22), which represent one of the case studies addressed by our Work Package (see reference to the case study). The relation with the physical object E22 Human-Made Object and/or the epigraphic field is represented by TX4 Writing Field, which is also a subclass of E25 and it describes the portion of the physical carrier arranged and usually reserved and delimited for the purpose of accommodating a written text. The link between object and text refers not only to the entities but also to the history of the text and the object. The description of the events linked to the physical object, its hardcopies and digital reproductions can be represented by using the activities and classes of CIDOC-CRM and the extensions. Those that are selected in the realization of the CRMtex are the CRMsci, CRMinf and FRBRoo. Among these classes, we can highlight, as an example, **TX3 Writing System**, a subclass of **E29 Design or Procedure**, which is used to produce a **TX1 Written Text** during a **TX2 Writing** event (in the case of the magic bowls, the Arabic alphabet used to inscribe various therapeutic formulas or verses from the Quran, see below). The other important binome consists of the difference between the graphic marks and the specific linguistic utterances represented in a written form. In order to formalize the processes that are at the base of the management and study of texts, the first aim of CRMtex was therefore to identify and define in a clear and unambiguous way the main entities involved in the study and edition of ancient and other handwritten texts and then to describe them by means of appropriate ontological instruments. Since the core concept of the model is the notion of "text" as the product of a semiotic process, CRMtex tries to deepen the close relationships existing between fragments of text or sequences of signs and the underlying meaning they were originally intended to convey. According to semiotic theory, language and writing are

²⁵ Definition of the CRMtex. An Extension of CIDOC CRM to Model Ancient Textual Entities (http://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmtext/fm_releases)

codes, and transmission of a message is a process of coding and decoding. Coding consists in assigning the appropriate expression to a given content that is represented in CRMtex as TX2 Writing with reference to the activity of communicating information by means of permanent, visible marks through the use of specific tools (in the case of the magic bowls, the engraving process on the metallic support that resulted in the creation of the texts, see below). In this framework, the writing is characterized by the physical and conceptual signs that in the models are represented by the classes TX9 Glyph and TX8 Grapheme, referring to abstract units with distinctive value that can be phonemes, syllables, or complete words, depending on the writing system. The decoding consists in identifying the content starting from the expression. In the model, it is divided in two processes represented by two classes: TX5 Text Recognition is the class that describes activities of recognizing physical features on some surface; TX14 Reading the process of the reading that is “a highly complex activity involving the interplay of visual-perceptual, linguistic and conceptual systems” (Coulmas 1999: 430). In the case of CRMtex, it has been assumed that the decoding process is performed by scholars who usually produce more than one reading and reproduction of the text for research and scientific dissemination purposes. The class created to represent the process of reproduction of the text, or a particular sequence of the text is TX6 Transliteration that refers to activities of exactly re-writing (i.e., re-encoding) an instance of TX12 Grapheme Sequence by using a writing system different from that of the original text. In the study of texts or particular segments of them (TX7 Written Text Segment), the stylistic variations of hand-written texts are fundamental for the paleographic studies and the determination of the date and provenance. For this reason, it has been modeled the class TX10 Style.

Figure 9 CRMtex model. (http://www.cidoc-crm.org/crmtext/fm_releases)

6 Magic-Therapeutic Bowls: A Case Study of Art, Text, and New Technologies

One of the research cases explored by WP10 focuses on a unique category of objects commonly referred to in literature as *magic bowls* (Canova 1995) or *magic-therapeutic bowls* (Giunta 2018). These are distinctive vessels, most commonly crafted from metal alloys like bronze or brass, although examples made of wood or ceramic can also be found. The bowls are generally hemispherical, lacking a base, with straight or occasionally slightly rounded rims. Their dimensions are usually modest, ranging from approximately 10 to 20 cm in diameter, and some feature a raised central element on the inside. Occasionally, perforations along the rim suggest that the bowls could be suspended or that a string of tablets could be attached to them. Whether placed around the outer edge of the rim or encircling the central protrusion, these tablets would have produced a rattling sound during use.²⁶

Regarding the chronology, it is likely that morpho-typological variations also indicate chronological differences; however, since most of the material originates from the antiquities market, reconstructing the history and modifications occurred in the style of these objects proves challenging.

Therapeutic-magic bowls served a variety of purposes, addressing a broad spectrum of health concerns. These vessels were believed to counteract the venom of scorpions and snakes—a theme frequently mentioned in their inscriptions and occasionally illustrated on their inner surfaces. They were also placed on the abdomens of women to assist during childbirth, utilized to relieve digestive ailments, protect against the malevolent influence of the evil eye, and soothe overly restless children. Their multifunctional nature highlights their significance in both medical and ritualistic practices.

The bowls feature numerous inscriptions, primarily in Arabic, though some are in Persian and, more rarely, in unintelligible scripts. The inscriptions are arranged in different ways: therapeutic texts often form continuous bands along the outer rim, following the circular contour of the bowl, while others are isolated, positioned amidst decorative or symbolic motifs (squares, stars, cartouches) on both the interior and exterior surfaces.

The textual content is highly varied. Some inscriptions are overtly religious, such as Koranic verses with the sporadic occurrence of the *šahāda* (the Islamic declaration of belief in the unity of God and the prophethood of Muhammad), the *tašliyya*, one of the 99 Names of God or short expressions declaring the power of God. Others consist of therapeutic formulas. In such cases, the formulas were inscribed beneath the exterior rim, within a frame.

In addition to these inscriptions, the bowls often contain "documentary" information, including references to political or religious authorities, dates and places of production, instructions for use, artisan names, and favourable astrological alignments. Pseudo-

²⁶ <https://exhibitions.kelsey.lsa.umich.edu/pearls/objects/bowl2.html>.

inscriptions occur as well, generally in Arabic characters (both letters and numbers), but also in characters inspired by Greek, Hebrew and Aramaic alphabets. “Planetary characters”, it means straight or curving strokes with circular extremities, are attested, generally placed at the closure of Arabic texts.

Inscriptions also feature single words, letters, numbers, symbols such as the Seal of Solomon, and magic squares. Animal motifs—snakes, scorpions, lizards, quadrupeds, and dragons—are common, as are zodiacal and astrological symbols and depictions of human figures. Texts, symbols, and iconographic elements were engraved both inside and outside the bowls, often framed within cartouches, medallions, or borders, or arranged in geometric or geometric-vegetal compositions.

To enhance the readability of the inscriptions, they were often filled with a blackish-yellow substance resembling niello, later replaced with silver in more refined productions.

Bowls were filled with liquids like water, oil, milk, or honey. Once the liquid was believed to have absorbed the power of the inscribed words—potentially over several days—it was administered to the patient. Due to the frequent inclusion of Allah’s name, these bowls were known in certain regions, such as Yemen, as *tāsat al-ism*, literally *bowls of the Name* (Sarnelli 1934; Oman 1995).

These bowls were not utilitarian items; they were heirlooms passed down through generations, preserved by prominent families. Their status as “magical” objects are underscored by the fact that the engravers were not ordinary artisans but individuals with expertise in religion, astronomy, magic, philosophy, metalworking, and engraving techniques. Tradition holds that these containers were initially used by *jinn* before being adopted by humans. In the Islamic world, the production of these objects continued well into relatively recent times, the 19th and even the 20th century.

The corpus examined within the frame of ReTina by WP10 is part of a donation to the Oriental Museum “Umberto Scerrato”, included in the university museum system of the University of Naples L’Orientale. The donation was made by Armando Tagliacozzo, the owner of the Aron Collection, an important private English collection of Islamic metalwork. Among the objects, 21 bowls are of Iranian origin, while 14 specimens are from the Near East (Giunta 2018). In addition to these 35 studied bowls, there are 79 others currently under study. This assemblage of magic-therapeutic bowls ranks among the most extensive collections of its kind worldwide, likely surpassed only by the one in Cairo, and serves as a highlight of the university’s museum system.

Given the focus of WP10 within the project—the analysis of religious texts from the Nile Valley and beyond—we found it an ideal opportunity to study this *corpus*, not only for its inherent significance and importance, but also for the unique challenges this type of material presents. These objects are valuable not only as works of art, representing a specific cultural context and conveying technological knowledge, but also for the symbolic and decorative elements that add deeper meanings to both the surfaces they adorn and the

inscriptions they carry. In this regard, it is essential to highlight that the inscriptions are inseparable from their physical support. The full meaning of an inscription cannot be understood without considering the object or monument it is associated with, just as the nature of that object cannot be fully comprehended without examining the inscription or iconography it bears. Furthermore, the inscription itself has physical characteristics that carry meaning and provide valuable information that transcends the text's literal content. The style of the letters, their spacing, orientation, technique, and other details offer crucial clues about the era, creators, and purpose of the inscription.

Since these objects are part of the university's museum system, WP10 was required to provide a detailed cataloguing of the bowls as its first deliverable, following the standards set by the Italian Central Institute for Cataloguing and Documentation (ICCD). Consequently, RA (*Reperto Archeologico*/Archaeological Object) forms were completed, which provide a substantial amount of information about the archaeological items (the form includes 300 fields and subfields, divided into 20 sections). However, these forms present several challenges, such as the use of vocabulary (both open and closed, exclusively in Italian). The same issue arose with the cataloguing of the inscriptions, which were registered using EP in-depth forms (*Modulo di approfondimento per epigrafi*, essentially an epigraph form), also based on a model provided by the ICCD, one for each inscription on the bowls.

This type of cataloguing works well within the Italian system, but it becomes limiting and difficult to use in an international context and within the scope of the project itself. It compromises the efficient use of data and similarly hinders the mapping activity, effectively complicating the process of linking the fields of one database to those of another.

To address this limitation, WP10 has converted the extensive data from the RA form into the CIDOC-CRM format and the EP form into the CIDOC-CRMTex format.

The use of metadata and thesauri enables the integration of the various components' descriptions and supports data sharing, following the FAIR principles of Open Science. This approach overcomes the limitations of traditional documentation.

However, the greatest challenge perhaps lies in attempting to automate the segmentation process of the different components that characterize these artifacts, which include not only inscriptions but also symbols. To facilitate the study of these objects in all their components, high-resolution three-dimensional scans of the bowls have been acquired, with the aim of creating digital replicas, thanks to the collaboration of experts from the University of Naples, L'Orientale. These replicas could aid in comprehensive analysis, offering a deeper understanding of the objects and the relationships between their various components.

Conclusions

The activities carried out under D10.2 show the impossibility of defining a single and exclusive data model that could facilitate the standardization of different datasets. We have also shown how the ambiguity of the objects, the historical and scientific separation between the archaeological find and the inscription, even if on the same artifact, have led to different digitization results, which are often difficult to integrate.

The test conducted on the magic cups shows the difficulty of a process that starting from a national standard can then end with the use of a standard metadata schema. The use of CRMTex certainly facilitates the association of media with text, but it remains a schema that should then be aligned on other higher-level standards to ensure the best semantic interoperability.

Likewise, the use of the other data-models also adopted by some European research infrastructures and described in this deliverable would not guarantee proper integration being specific either to the scope of the archaeological find (AO-CAT) or to the inscriptions (EAGLE). The other standards such as EDM or Schema.org are too generalist and generic to offer scholars of religions semantically rich datasets; imed primarily at publishing data online these two standards allow very narrow descriptions of objects preferring rather to define the relationship between the digital resource and its destination on the Web.

Tests to be conducted in the coming months on other datasets will likely identify additional critical issues and perhaps define a more correct procedure for standardizing resources and integrating them without penalizing the complete description of the physical object and the transcription, transliteration and interpretation of the text.

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